

SEMANTIC AND GRAMMATICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ATTITUDES

Alijonova Fotima Odiljon qizi

Namangan city school No. 37 teacher of native language and literature, master
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617563>

Abstract: In this article, the analysis of research and scientific-theoretical views on the semantic and grammatical features of idioms is carried out.

Key words: ravish, semantics, grammar, word structure, meaning, sit, kisra, karu .

Attributive words refer to the sign of an action, the sign of a sign (adjective or attitude), and sometimes the sign of an object. When Ravish indicates the sign of an action, it shows the process, state, time, place of execution. Coming before an adjective or adverb, it shows the degree of the sign in them, and before a noun, it means that the object sign is similar to another sign or an adjective sign.

Ravish, like other word groups, has its own morphological features:

The main morphological feature of ravish is its invariance, that is, when ravish forms a compound by connecting with a word, it does not change its form, it does not receive any word-changing affix.

The fact that Ravish has its own formative affixes is also considered its morphological feature: -chasiga (mardcha), -larcha (barbarian), iga -siga (transverse, lengthwise), -lab (week-lip), -cha (like a soldier, around, in a hurry), like -dek, -day (like a bullet, like a stone).

In terms of structure, some adverbs are similar to nouns that have taken the form of agreement (down, basically) and pronouns (so, then, then), adjectives (slowly, babbaravar), adverbs (in the morning, gradually, steadily). This similarity is not a random phenomenon, but while the ravish was being formed as a group of words, it filled its composition with words separated from those groups. There are even such idioms that today have completely moved away from their original forms: forward, tens, four, out, again.

Adjectives are often attached to verbs. For example, Ergash still didn't know enough about the insidious enemy who stands next to you during the day and talks sugar talk, and who comes out of hiding and stabs you in the shoulder at night. (A. Mukhtar) In some cases, ravish can be connected to adjectives and nouns, as well as a little ravish: A little intelligence is better than a lot of wealth. (Proverb.) On that day, Usmanov returned home very late. (O'. Umarbekov). The main grammatical features of the verb are that it does not have the

characteristic of type and declension, it is often connected to the verb and acts as a case:

Since it is a denotative word, adjectives are close to adjectives. Ravishes have the characteristic of gradating the sign of movement and character as quality, showing them in a staggered fashion: Zainab entered earlier, Kumush entered later. (A. Qadiri) But in terms of character, function, and connection to other words, ravishes differ from quality. The adjective is mainly attached to the noun, indicates a fixed sign specific to the subject and acts as a qualifier. Verbs are mainly related to the verb, signifying the sign of the action, the connection with the process, and act as a case: Muhiddin and Salimjan went inside, asking for permission. (A. Mukhtar) In the Uzbek language, it is a common phenomenon that a word from one group is left behind a word from another group. This situation is also characteristic of the use of quality management.

Some adjectives are attached to the verb and indicate the action, come in the adverbial form and perform the function of the case: Ahmadjan boya was very quiet. It is impossible to speak badly about a person without getting to know him better. (A. Qahhor) Verbs attached to a noun and indicating the sign of an object can sometimes become a noun. At this time, adverbs accept the noun-specific agreement, possessive and plural affixes and act as possessors, complementors, orientators in the sentence.

Also, in some ravishes, word-changing forms are found. Ravish may contain the agreement affix, the plural -s and the third person possessive form -i. These word-modifying adverbs slightly change the lexical-semantic content of the word.

Conjugation forms in adverbs mainly have two different characteristics: in one place, the vargai vargai suffix has a different meaning, for example: after - after - after, before - in front - forward; in other places, the adverb does not change in meaning, but acquires an additional meaning (strengthening or clarifying the meaning), for example: in the morning - in the morning - from the morning, now - now - from now, quickly - quickly - as soon as: First think, then speak (Proverb). Let's do something first (Oybek).

The plural suffix -lar indicates continuity and uncertainty in the context. like before - before, before - before, already - like before. The third person possessive affix is used together with the plural:

Ravishes are made mainly in two ways:

by affixation;

by composition.

Affixation has existed in our language for a long time, and it has become the most effective method, especially in later times. Verbal forms are divided into productive and unproductive affixes: -cha, -larcha, chasiga, -iga, siga -lab, -deb, -day are productive forms: -ona, -an, -n (-in), -lay, -simon, etc. are useless formatives.

-cha affix joins nouns, adjectives, pronouns, adjectives and adverbs to form adverbs. With the help of this affix, the formation of ravish from nouns is somewhat developed, and the formation of ravish from other categories is quite limited.

Adverbs formed with the help of -cha mean the way of performing the action, the level, the similarity of the sign: friendly, Russian, doomsday, military, as before, new, as good, as good, as much, as you think, as much as you want, while running, for now, often, as later. The formative affix -cha can be attached directly to the stem (military+cha, biz+cha) and it can also be added after possessive and agreement affixes (its +i+cha, we+ning + cha).

The adverbs formed with the help of -larcha do not differ in meaning from the adverbs formed through -cha, the meaning of simile formed with the affix -larcha is a little stronger: mardlarcha - mardcha, dostrachcha - dostcha.

The affix -larcha usually forms a verb from a noun or an adjective:

like brothers, comrades, sons, children, fathers, ages, loved ones, guilty, careless, savages.

With the affix -chasiga, adverbs are formed mainly from nouns and sometimes adjectives. These idioms indicate the complete similarity of the sign of action in terms of meaning: like a hero, a warrior, a hero, a tashkentky, an open man, a summer man.

The formative affixes -chasiga and -larcha are complex in terms of content, and the formative form -cha is the basis for the formation of each case. In the further development of our language, the affixes -cha, -larcha, -chasiga became independent formants.

Verbs formed with the help of the affixes -iga// -siga indicate how the sign of action is semantically performed and similar: to the side, to the length, to the whole, to the side, like a liar, a liar, a real person, a chronic person;

-iga/siga affixes are usually added to nouns, adjectives, pronouns, adverbs and adverbs to form adverbs; -siga (yalpi+siga) is added to words ending with a vowel, and -iga (birikay+iga) is added to words ending with a consonant.

Sometimes, in words ending with a consonant, the sound a is added between the stem and the affix: long+a+sigā, row+a+sigā.

It is shown that the affixes -dek//day are added to nouns, adjectives, pronouns, and sometimes other words to form adverbs. In the literature of the later period, these are considered additional simile loadings.

With the help of the affix -lab, adverbs are formed from nouns or words of another category, meaning state, time and amount-level: in the morning, yesterday, weeks, months, years, letters, one by one, tons, tons, tons, hectares, like many.

Adverbs made with the help of the mother affix mean imitation and simile: friendly, modest, objective, reasonable, old-fashioned, weak, proud, insidious, for example:

The affix -ona came from the Persian-Tajik language and as a formative is equivalent to the affixes -larcha, chasigā; in the next, the growth and expansion of the creative role made the suffix -ona ineffective.

The affix -an is the accusative form of the Arabic language, and in the words that come from that language, it has the function of adverbial formation. With this affix, adverbs indicating the state of performance of the action are formed: partially, really, strictly, apparently, mentally, conscientiously, completely, in response, forcibly, mentally.

Adverbs formed with the help of the affix -lay//-layin indicate the sign of action: alive, like completely.

The second main method of making ravish is composition. By composition, words are joined together, arranged or repeated, resulting in a phrase. Making a ravish in this way cannot be completely equated with the same kind of making in another category. When forming by adding words, we observe the presence of morphological forms in some idioms: - in one place, to this side, from here, from day to day, from time to time, in vain, in a row, in a row such as. These forms are important in making a joint ravish.

Despite the fact that some of the combined expressions that make up a certain synonymous series are formed from the participation of words, there is a difference in their morphological formation: one way, one way, one way, one way; by the way, by the way, by the way; all the time, all the time, every now and then; day by day, day by day, day by day; nari beri, like far and wide.

Phrases formed by adding words can include different word groups, they are as follows:

After demonstrative pronouns *y, by, my, yxo*, by quoting the words *yer, yak, ara*, mid in the form of locative agreements: to there, here, from here, there from the side, meanwhile, as in the middle.

Demonstrative pronouns are sometimes combined with nouns denoting the moment in the form of head or locative agreements to form adverbs: this day, this day, that time, that time, that time, that moment, that moment, that time, that time.

The marking pronoun "every" is from the addition of words in the form of head or locative agreements: to every side, everywhere. everywhere, wherever, whenever, whenever, every moment as:

By combining one word with the words in the head or position agreement: one way, one day, one day, one year, one time, one moment, one pas, one below, one pasga, one breath, in one breath, in one breath, for a moment, for a time, at the same time, for a time, for a time, for a time, from the same head, as a whole, as a whole, as a child, as a like a little, a handful, a talai.

The repetition of words is also a useful method.

In general, the main semantic function of the word in reduplication is generalization. If the repeated words remain within their category, the sense of generalization prevails; When words move out of their category through repetition, a new word is usually formed.

Repetition (pairing) in the framework of idioms tends to give new meaning along with generalization: in idioms such as *nari-beri* (fast), *little-by-goz*, *kam-kam* (slowly), *ucha-muncha*, *hali-beri*, a new meaning is felt. Pairings such as *often*, *very-very*, and *slowly* have arisen due to the strengthening of the meaning of the word or special attention being paid to it. Phrases made by repetition of words can be divided into three types according to their morphological formation:

words are repeated in the capital form: abundant, safe, poor, poor, earlier, earlier, later, as soon as:

when words are repeated, connect them in pairs

morphological form-agreement affixes are used for: *day-by-day*, *day-by-day*, *year-by-year*, *year-by-year*, *open-open*, *void-void*, *void-void*, *sleep-void*, rarely, like

c) add the element *-ma* (*-ba*) to connect adverbs made by repetition: successively, layer by layer, *kunma-kun* (*kun-bakun*), *damma-dam* (*dambadam*), *zor-bazor*, like *zinhor-bazinhor*.

repeated words into idioms is the lexical-semantic and grammatical change that has occurred in them. Due to this, the pair of words becomes a phrase out of the scope of its category.

Almost all independent word groups are involved in the formation of syllables by repetition of words, but the degree of formation is not the same. It is more common to form ravishes from nouns with repetition than in other categories.

Material types of ravishes made by repetition are as follows:

Horse with horse. By repetition of nouns, the formation of a ravis can be through all three types of morphological formation indicated: repetition, row-row, night-day, almost-about, head-to-head, year-to-year, turn-by-turn, back-to-back. like back, alternately, face to face, three by three, step by step.

Quality with quality. Verbs made by repeating adjectives can also be of three types in terms of morphological formation: safe-safe, other-other, some-some, some-some, pishyk-pishyk, openly-openly, directly ri, like zorma-raki.

Verbs are formed by repetition of verb forms: uzil-kesil, agdartontar, take-put, know-know, see-see (put-not-put, put-not-put), more and more, more and more, more and more, more and more, and more and more.

Treat with treat. Repeated idioms give a new meaning and acquire a new word character: nari-beri, naridan- since, before-after, before-after, one-by-one, then-this, still-beri.

Pronouns, numbers, exclamations and mixed words are formed by repetition of words: by himself, by himself, by himself, by himself, by himself, one by one, apil-tapil, taka-tak, conditionally-conditionally, open-clearly, completely, along-the-way, helpless, time-to-time.

References:

1. Abdullaev A. Morphological method of meaning enhancement // Uzbek language and literature, 1970, issue 1. - B. 24-27.
- 2 . Asadov T.A. About the Ravish vocabulary and its composition // Uzbek language and literature, 2005, issue 2. - B. 53-55.
3. Asadov T. _ Word categories in the system ravish : Philol . science _ name _ ... dis . autoref . - Tashkent , 2009. -23 p .
4. Alamova M. Semantic-stylistic characteristics of accretive forms // Collection of scientific works of ToshDU, No. 648. - Tashkent, 1980. - B. 61-65.
5. Bozorov O. Grading in Uzbek: Philology. science. doctor... dis. afterref. - Tashkent, 1997.

